

τότε ἔλεγεν αὐτοῖς

Narrative Structure and Eschatological Timing in Luke 21:10

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

ABSTRACT

Luke alone records a pause at Luke 21:10, a narrative detail often overlooked by commentators. This study examines the literary and theological significance of that pause within Jesus’s eschatological discourse. It argues that the formula marks a transition between preliminary disturbances—wars, disorders and false expectations that do not signal the immediate end—and the composite sign of the συντέλεια. By its form, the lacuna mirrors the temporal interval it describes, creating space for a global witness before the τέλος arrives.

Luke 21:10

τότε ἔλεγεν αὐτοῖς ἐγερθήσεται ἔθνος ἐπ’ ἔθνος καὶ βασιλεία ἐπὶ βασιλείαν

MATTHEW 24	MARK 13	LUKE 21
6 You are going to hear of wars and reports of wars;	7 Moreover, when you hear of wars and reports of wars,	9 Furthermore, when you hear of wars
see that you are not	do not be	and disorders,
terrified. For	terrified;	do not be
these things must take place,	[these things] must take place,	terrified.
but the end is not yet.	but the end is not yet.	For
¶7 “For	¶8 “For	these things must occur
nation will rise against nation and kingdom against kingdom,	nation will rise against nation and kingdom against kingdom,	first,
and	there will be 2 food shortages	but the end does not [occur] immediately.”
there will be 1 food shortages		¶10 Then he went on to say to them:
		“Nation will rise against nation, and kingdom against kingdom;
		11 and
		there will be 3 food shortages

and	there will be	
2 earthquakes	1 earthquakes	great
in one place after another.	in one place after another,	1 earthquakes,
		and
		in one place after another
		2 pestilences;
		and there will be fearful sights and from
		heaven great signs.
8 All	These	
these		
things		
are a beginning of pangs of distress.	are a beginning of pangs of distress.	

Only Luke records this pause. Not many commentators notice it. Here are two: Expositor's: "τότε ἔλεγεν points to a new beginning in discourse, which has the effect of dissociating the repeated mention of political disturbances from what goes before, and connecting it with apostolic tribulations referred to in the sequel. In Mt. and Mk. the verse corresponding is simply an expansion of the previous thought."

Bengel: "It is indicated by the introduction of this formula, that a short pause intervened before He spake".

As the disciples were discussing the temple in Jerusalem, Jesus had told them, "As for these things that YOU are beholding, the days will come in which not a stone upon a stone will be left here and not be thrown down" (Luke 21:6). This prompted the disciples to ask, "When will these things actually be, and what will be the sign when these things are destined to occur?" (verse 7), or as Matthew recorded it, "Tell us, when will these things be, and what will be the sign of your presence and of the conclusion of the system of things? (24:3). By asking these questions, the disciples might have thought that the destruction of Jerusalem would occur at the same time as the συντελείας τοῦ αἰῶνος, "the conclusion of the system of things". Instead, Jesus divided the two. Jesus's response refers "not to one event but to two, and that the first was typical of the second.... [Jesus] places an indefinite interval between the fall of Jerusalem and the end of the world" (Dummelow).

In the Luke account Jesus answered their questions:

8 He said: "Look out that YOU are not misled; for many will come on the basis

of my name, saying, 'I am he,' and, 'The due time has approached.' Do not go after them. 9 Furthermore, when you hear of wars and disorders, do not be terrified. For these things must occur first, but the end does not [occur] immediately."

As Jesus foretold, "It appears that in the first century before the destruction of the Temple a number of Messiahs arose promising relief from the Roman yoke, and finding ready followers" (JE). Also, there would be a number of "wars and disorders" during this period that would affect the Jewish nation. "But Christ's disciples were not to be terrified into taking premature action" (w 1974, p. 682). Hence Jesus said, δὲ γὰρ ταῦτα γενέσθαι πρῶτον ἀλλ' οὐκ εὐθέως τὸ τέλος, "these things must occur first, but the end does not [occur] immediately".

In Matthew 24:3 the disciples had asked when the συντελείας τοῦ αἰῶνος would be. Concerning συντελείας, *nwtsty* says it means "'joint end; combination end; ending together.'" (Mt 13:39, 40, 49; 28:20; Heb 9:26) This refers to a time period during which a combination of events would lead to the complete "end" mentioned at Mt 24:6, 14, where a different Greek word, *te'los*, is used".

Although Jesus does not know when the end will come (Matthew 24:36), he does intimate that the complete end would be sometime off (w 1964, p. 677).

Jesus then paused.

It looks as if he went on to make a distinction between the magnitude of the wars.

10 Then he went on to say to them: "Nation will rise against nation, and kingdom against kingdom; 11 and there will be great earthquakes, and in one place after another pestilences and food shortages; and there will be fearful sights and from heaven great signs."

"So it would not be a case of just hearing of an isolated war here and there. This feature of the sign would take in many nations and kingdoms. It would be total war" (w 1983 4/1 p. 4).

Matthew's account has:

7 For nation will rise against nation and kingdom against kingdom, and there will be food shortages and earthquakes in one place after another. 8 All these things are a beginning of pangs of distress.

The disciples would go from *hearing* of "wars and disturbances" (NW, 2013) to being engulfed by them. When they *experienced* this, they would know that these

were the beginnings of pangs of distress (ὠδίνων). ὠδίν “refers to the intense pain experienced during childbirth. While it is used here to refer to distress, pain, and suffering in a general sense, it may suggest that like birth pains the foretold troubles and suffering will increase in frequency, intensity, and duration in the time period before the great tribulation mentioned at Mt 24:21” (*nwtsty*).

Jesus told his disciples that the ‘hearing of wars and reports of wars and disturbances’ would not signify the τέλος, the end, quite yet, but once the wars are global—whole nations rising against whole nations, ἔθνος ἐπὶ ἔθνος, people against people—then his disciples would know that they had entered the final phase. Indeed, the all-encompassing wars would be part of the composite sign that would include “great earthquakes, and in one place after another pestilences and food shortages; and there will be fearful sights and from heaven great signs” (Luke 21:11). This composite sign is the συντελείας, the combination of events that would lead to the complete τέλος.

So the pause comes after a pastoral reassuring comment—calming the premature alarm and correcting the expectation of his disciples—and before a catalogue of events that would indicate the end is imminent. It would have slowed the disciples’ instinct to equate turmoil with imminence, before reopening the answer with further specifics.

The pause was a transition from small to big—scattered reports of war to international upheaval, something that the disciples could not escape *experiencing*. Connected with that, there is the movement from verse 9 ἀκούσητε, “hearing”, to pause, to ἐγερθήσεται, “will rise”, a movement of hearing, pause, seeing.

Perhaps too, the pause is playing out the temporal pause between ‘the end is not yet’ and ‘the end is nigh’—the very delay it was describing—the form mirroring the content.

This gap in time allowed the disciples an opportunity to bear witness to everyone (Acts 1:7, 8; *w* 1970, p. 715; Dummelow), as Jesus went on to say: “This good news of the kingdom will be preached in all the inhabited earth for a witness to all the nations; and then the end (τέλος) will come” (Matthew 24:14).

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bengel John Albert Bengel, *Gnomon of the New Testament*, translated by Andrew R. Fausset, T&T Clarke, 1866.
- Dummelow J. R. Dummelow, *The One Volume Bible Commentary*, The MacMillan Company, 1936.
- Expositor's *The Expositor's Bible Commentary*, Zondervan, 1984.
- JE *The Jewish encyclopedia: a descriptive record of the history, religion, literature, and customs of the Jewish people from the earliest times to the present day*, edited by Isidore Singer, Funk and Wagnalls, 1901.
- NW, 2013 *New World Translation Study Edition*, Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, Inc., Wallkill, New York, 2013.
- nwtsty* *New World Translation Study Edition notes*, Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, Inc., Wallkill, New York, 2013.
- w* *The Watchtower*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “you” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.